

Discere hypothesis - a potential supplement to cell theory

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Running title: Discere hypothesis

Keywords: cell theory, gasocrine hypothesis, cellular memory

For reasons that remain unclear, despite roughly 4 billion years of cellular evolution, cell theory has only three well-accepted postulates¹. I previously proposed the gasocrine, circumiacentium, informatio, and conscientia hypotheses, which state that all cells require gasocrine signaling², are limited by their environment³, pass information⁴, and require consciousness⁵, respectively. I also proposed cellular consciousness is the sum of its endogenous and environmental signaling or simply sum of its signaling activities⁵. But if a cell can be considered conscious, how does it know it is conscious if it has not learned about itself or its environment? Therefore, I propose *all cells learn*. This hypothesis can be falsified by identifying a cell that is unable to learn or lacks cellular processes that constitute a form of molecular memory and learning⁶⁻⁹. Therefore, this hypothesis is a potential supplement to cell theory.

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